

“RESEARCH-BASED TRANSFORMATION OF TEACHER EDUCATION: TRADITION AS A BASIS FOR INNOVATION” International Conference on Teacher Education

CONCEPTION OF TEACHING ENGLISH IN THE HIGHER EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM

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***Annotation.** The reformations taking place in Uzbekistan, along with the expansion of industrial production, are first of all imitated in the educational system. The goal of the thesis is to establish cooperation of the educational system institutions with production innovativeness. In order to advance the quality of training of highly competent personnel and to endorse foreign cooperation's, it is important to attain international level in foreign languages training. According to the results of the directed research, mutual cooperation relations were achieved between students and teachers of higher educational institutions, students of general education schools and academic lyceums and employers of specialized industrial departments. As a conclusion, it can be said that the effective method of teaching English in non-philological education areas based on the cluster approach in accordance with specialties was verified by statistical methods during the research.*

***Key words:** teaching English, higher education, cluster approach, continued education, module, non-philological sphere, specialized industrial departments.*

INTRODUCTION

Prime scientific centers and researchers in the world are carrying out scientific research on the internationalization of the personnel training procedure related to the development of cooperation based on cluster approaches in the system of comprehensive education and production integration. According to the tasks defined in the UNESCO Global Convention on Education (2019) [Abdisamatov.A., 2022; 30], a special attention should be paid to learning a foreign language at educational institutions based on the cluster system. It is proved that education enables young people to improve creative thinking skills and innovative development. Accordingly, in assembly with the development of continuous education, integration of science and production, scientific research is being carried out in promising directions to improve the mechanisms of forming the scientific and theoretical foundations of the innovative cluster in the system of continuous education [Mikhailova, M., 2018; 49].

Innovation clusters in the educational system are higher education and scientific research institutions located in a certain environment, including production, where all participants in the chain system created (scientific institutions, small innovative companies, testing centers, centrally used equipment, product certifiers) laboratories, higher educational institutions and centers that train specialists and send them to places, intellectual property agency, etc.) are interactive and collaborative activities

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from the beginning to the end of creating an innovative product [Anistsyna N.N., 2010; 91]

It is fact that the last stage of the continued educational system is higher education. As a continuation of teaching English in step-by-step modules based on the cluster approach, teaching English to students of non-philological education, in particular, biology, based on cluster approaches, was determined in the tasks of the research which was held by us. A student who has studied English in the upper classes (10-11 grades) based on the cluster approach, studies English at the university system as a continuation of this system [Kushieva N., 2020; 78]. The principles noted in the modular system formed on the basis of our experimental work and systematic training based on the module were taken as a basis and efficiency indicators were achieved. According to this system, communication in English (General English), description of specialized resources in English (Introduction to the biological sphere), being able to express and communicate one's opinion in the specialty (Communicating in biology sphere), mastering foreign resources on agriculture and expanding one's worldview (Developing natural sciences outlook), providing information about industry news and technologies in English (Integration of education and production) are supposed to have such aspect (see table 1).

Table 1

Modular stages of teaching English to the students of biology sphere (non-philological sphere)

Module number	Modules (General themes)	Hours
1	General English	126
2	Introduction to the biological sphere	126
3	Communicating in biology sphere	126
4	Developing natural sciences outlook	126
5	Integration of education and production	126
Total: 5		630

1. General English

During these studies, the General English module focused on the development of communication skills of biology students in professional and non-professional

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situations, interviews, conversations, telephone conversations, the use of gestures and reading various texts, and the development of communication skills by creating simple applications

2. Introduction to the biological sphere (non-philological sphere)

"Introduction to the biological sphere" is taught in the 2nd semester of the 1st stage. The allocated class time for this semester is 78 hours. This semester focused on students, future biology majors, understanding their field and communicating key information to their peers and other groups. In this module, students will develop their language skills, including communicating their knowledge in a critical manner and English learning knowledge in such areas as, critical thinking, gathering information, problem solving, presenting ideas and searching for information, cause and effect while learning the language.

3. Communicating in the biology sphere

"Communicating in biology sphere" is a communicative module of language teaching, which is effectively used today in Europe and the USA. As the name implies, this module is based on interaction, where reading, writing, speaking and understanding dialogues are essential, which form the basis of any language learning. Of course, in this module, teachers pay more attention to the last two methods (conversation and understanding of dialogues) and complex word devices and serious lexis are not encountered in the activities dedicated to this module. The only problem encountered in this module is that students in the experimented groups mastered the words related to the field, students easily understood the content of the texts related to their specialties, but it was difficult for them to engage in serious communication with the field specialist. The purpose of this module is primarily to overcome the fear of communication.

4. Developing natural sciences outlook

"Developing natural sciences outlook" is devoted to the 2nd semester of the 2nd stage of biology students. This module focused on developing oral and written skills of future professionals in their chosen field and focused on developing oral (telephone interview, teleconference, video conference) communication and written (e-mail, letters, formal requests, applications) skills in the field of biology. Moreover, according to the goals and tasks defined in this module, the experimental work carried out on the basis of the program created on the basis of the cluster approach was recorded as a continuation of the results of the module described above

5. Integration of Education and Production

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Integration of science and production biology course is intended for students of the 3rd stage, and at this stage the English language is studied only for 1 semester. The focus of this module is on developing language skills, participating in tenders, conducting meetings, submitting reports, and building capacity in the fields of biology. The purpose of the module is to develop students' public speech, to enable the future biology specialists to describe in English the process from product preparation to production. This, in turn, became the basis for teaching English based on cluster approaches. That is, the process from product preparation to production was mastered by students in the higher educational system not only through the studied specialty subjects, but also in English, and the ground was created for the development of professional personnel. Accordingly, the experimental work conducted on the module, which was created on the basis of the cluster approach, according to the goals and tasks defined in this module, gave positive results as a continuation of the results of the module mentioned above

CONCLUSION

Training an educated, modern-thinking young generation based on the goals and tasks set in the continuous education system is important in creating a system aimed at further integration of the Republic into the world community. Thus, according to the results of the research, the application of the modules formed on the basis of cluster approaches in the non-philological educational areas of higher educational institutions, in particular, in the areas of biology, made it possible to achieve positive results. The reliability of the research results and conclusions is explained by the fact that the applied approach, methods and data are obtained from official sources, that the presented analyses and the effectiveness of experimental tests are scientifically based on mathematical-statistical methods, that the conclusions, suggestions and recommendations are put into practice, and that the obtained results are confirmed by authorized structures.

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